

A DESCRIPTION OF METHODS FOR ANALYZING RAILROAD TERMINOLOGY AS A LINGUISTIC COMPONENT FOR PARTICULAR OBJECTIVES (ON THE MATERIAL OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE)

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Abstract. *The subject of this research is the approaches towards studying railway terminology as the language for specific purposes. Transport and namely railway terminology holds an important place in the terminological system of English language. The author explores the basic interpretations of the concept of “language for specific purposes”, as well as such approaches towards studying railway terminology of English language as semantic, structural and etymological. Semantic approach consists in classification of terms by semantic groups. Structural approach analyzes the number and nature of components that comprise terminological units in this area of LSP. Etymological approach reviews the origin and evolution of the meaning of terminological units. The scientific novelty consists in comprehensive description of the approaches towards studying language for specific purposes on the materials of professional field “railway transport”. Research methodology includes the analysis of scientific literature, analysis of dictionary definitions, comparative method, and diachronic analysis. The conclusion was made that the same approaches are applicable to the analysis of railway terminology and to the analysis of language for specific purposes of any other professional sphere. At the same time, systematicity and hierarchical pattern of the acquired classifications indicated a high level of formedness and systematization of terminology under review.*

Keywords: *review, terminology, LSP, railway transport, research, semantic approach, structural approach, etymological approach, term, vocabulary.*

An important aspect of modern linguistics is the study of language for specific purposes and terminology. E.S. Zakirova notes the fact that the question of the relationship between language and the non-linguistic professional knowledge it denotes is especially relevant in the modern world, and therefore the national-specific professional vision of the world is studied both in the cognitive and anthropocentric paradigm. According to E.S. Zakirova, the significant features of the system of terms related to a particular social sphere is that the terms are a product created for utilitarian use in a professional circle. Under the language for special purposes, we, following E.S. Zakirova, we understand the communicative means of communication between people united by professional knowledge.

Transport and, in particular, railway terminology occupies an important place in the terminological system of the English language. The subject of this article is the approaches to learning a language for special purposes based on the material of this professional field. The aim of the work is a comprehensive description of research in the field of English-language railway terminology. To achieve this goal, such methods as analysis of scientific literature, analysis of dictionary definitions, comparative method, diachronic analysis were used. Since it is impossible to consider approaches to the study of language for special purposes in the professional field of

the railway sphere without an analysis of approaches to the language for special purposes itself, it seems reasonable to first consider approaches to the study of language for special purposes in general.

It should be noted that the study of a language for special purposes is inextricably linked with scientific and technological progress and, in particular, with the development of international scientific and economic contacts in the 20th century. N.B. Gvishiani notes that the differentiation of scientific knowledge contributed to the growth of the need for international communication, which, in turn, led to the recognition of the concept of "language for special purposes". The first European symposium devoted to the problems of "language for special purposes" took place in 1977 in Vienna. Nowadays, it is generally recognized that each professional field has its own language system, consisting of special terms that allow communication based on specially oriented knowledge, that is, its own "language for special purposes". In modern linguistics, there are several definitions of language for specific purposes. Some of them are listed below in the article. A.I. Komarova writes that: "language for special purposes" is a specific kind of "language as a whole", which is used when communicating on a particular professional topic."

In the terminological dictionary V.A. Tatarinov gives the following definition: "language for special purposes" is a concept of functional stylistics, related to terminology, denoting a functional variety of natural language, limited to a special-industry sphere of communication." I.S. Kudashev proposes the following definition: "language for special purposes" is a set of natural or natural-artificial language means used in any branch of knowledge and / or activity mainly for the transfer of subject information and reflecting the conceptual apparatus that is not the property of most carriers of this national language."

V.F. Novodranova gives the definition of the "language for special purposes" in a cognitive way: "from the point of view of the cognitive-discursive approach, LSP is such a system of linguistic means of a national language that represents the knowledge structures that have developed in a certain period of the development of science and demonstrate the level of development achieved during this period in a particular subject area knowledge that is important for society and ensures its own development and progress. The concept of "language for special purposes" is inextricably linked with the concept of "term". In the "Dictionary-reference book of linguistic terms" D.E. Rosenthal, M.A. Telenkova gives the following interpretation of it: "a word or phrase that accurately denotes any concept used in science, technology, art."

L.A. Chernyshova notes the following: "terms, as linguistic signs, belong to the national language and are a means of knowing the world around us;

- being signs of fixing the results of the scientific activity of thinking, the terms reflect the scientific type of thinking;

- terminological units are an obligatory component of language means for special purposes. Speaking about the interaction of commonly used and terminological vocabulary in a professional text, one should note the remark of V.P. Danilenko about the vocabulary of the scientific style: three relatively independent layers stand out. It:

- non-terminological vocabulary, which includes significant and functional words of the general literary language;

- general scientific vocabulary, which includes special words of scientific usage in general;

- terminological vocabulary, which is based on special words of individual terminological systems.

According to Sh.S. Olmatova, the system of terms related to any scientific field is a product of the term creation of each person, with his personal awareness of the world around him and the conditions of his native language. Based on this, we can say that in different languages of the world there is a professional perception of the world around. The systems of terms in various industries used to convey specialized information have strongly pronounced utilitarian features and are addressed to a specific part of society. Creation of a system of terms in industries. The result of the development of scientific knowledge is the formation of terminology in various fields, as an association of special lexical units that nominate specialized concepts related to the professional field.

In general, characterizing the lexical side of a professional text, one can agree with the opinion of E.S. Zakirova that "verbalization of professional knowledge is carried out in a language for special purposes by means of lexico-semantic structures capable of conveying the essence of the main categories and concepts of science, technology and other areas of professional activity." As for the terminological system of railway transport, Sh.S. Olmatova that "when describing railway terminology, there are some specific difficulties inherent in this area caused by the process of continuous modification, especially if we take into account the increasing dynamics of technological processes and the formation of accompanying language names". Many words from railway vocabulary are simultaneously used in other terminological systems. Industry terminology of railway transport refers to technical areas of knowledge, the terminology of which is characterized by a high degree of specificity and is based on well-defined concepts.

The terminology of railway transport is described in detail in the works of E.V. Demishkevich, which clearly characterizes the main approaches to the description of railway terminology: the semantic approach, the structural approach and the etymological approach. The semantic approach consists in classifying terms into semantic groups. The structural approach analyzes the number and nature of the components that make up the terminological units of a given LSC area. The etymological approach considers the origin and development of the meaning of terminological units. The article "Thematic groups of English railway terms" provides a semantic classification. According to the author, 5 thematic groups can be distinguished within the framework of this system: cars and rolling stock; instruments and devices; technical operations; organization of the transportation process; track and track facilities.

The data is presented in Chart 1:

An analysis of the diagram shows that 1. The group "Travel and track facilities" is represented by 1436 terms. This is 46% of the total sample of 3264 terms, which allows us to put this group in first place in terms of the number of terms 2. The group "Organization of the transportation process" includes 22% (718) of the total number of terms, which puts it in second place 3. third place is the group "Instruments and devices", which is represented by 554 terms or 17% of the total volume. 4. The group "Machinery and rolling stock" contains 293 terms - 9.2%. 5. The smallest group are 263 terms related to "Technical operations". This is only 8.8% of the total number of terms. Based on the presented thematic groups, it can be argued that the terminology of railway transport in English is systemic. This confirms the fact that the presented terminology consists of a large number of related elements that form a whole system. The structure of railway terminology in English is an ordered structure. A distinctive feature for the above described thematic groups is the existence of semantic links and a stepped structure of elements.

According to the structure, all terms can be divided into four groups: simple, complex, phrasal terms, terminological combinations. The last group is also divided into bound and free. Extensive research in this area was also carried out by E.V. Demishkevich. In his study, E.V. Demishkevich points out that 20% of railway transport terms are simple. The following terms can be cited as an example: ballast - ballast, sleeper - shpala, hump - saralash tepaligi, switcher - manyovr lokomotivi. Terms that have two root morphemes are complex. As a percentage, they are only 7% of the total number of terms given in the study. Examples of complex terms are: maglev – magnit to'htagichli poyez, high-speed – tezyrar, piggy-back – yarim pritsepli.

Combinations of terms, where one of the elements can be replaced by a synonymous term, refer to free terminological combinations. The share of such combinations in English railway terminology is only 2%, for example, transfer station - transfer station. The largest group of terms is represented by related terminological combinations, and the number is 67% of all the terms studied. The following phrases can serve as examples: level crossing - temir yo'l kesishmasi, classification yard – saralash shahobchasi, switching point – yol o'zgartirgich, gondola car – yarimvagon.

4% of all terms in the railway terminology of the English language are combinations of phrasal type. The number of elements in such combinations can be from two to six. For example: signal on post - ustunli svetofor; train safety in operation - harakat xavfsizligi; engine track to engine house — depo yo'llari; impedance bond, with secondary winding — induktor-transformator; headway between consecutive trains — stantsiya oralig'i; guy rod. in tension — kontaktni to'xtatib turish chizig'i.

It should be emphasized that a substantial portion of the terminological system used in English railway terminology is borrowed. E.V. Demishkevich discusses 64% of borrowings, highlighting major Latin, French, and German borrowings as well as unique borrowings from Dutch, Italian, and Spanish. Similar information was acquired by Sh. S. Olatova, who claims that 31.4% of the terms used in English terminology are of Anglo-Saxon origin. As for the original terms of English origin, they include words from the English language that are frequently employed and used in the terminological sense, such as gate and barrier (commonly known as gates) and yard and station (commonly known as yards). Diagram 2 compares the statistical information acquired by the aforementioned researchers.

Diagram 2. Statistical analysis in the etymological approach

The analysis of railway terminology follows the same procedures as the analysis of language used for specific objectives in any other professional sector, as can be seen from the description above. The systematic and hierarchical nature of the classifications discovered through analysis also points to a high level of industry-specific terminology formation and systematization, which accurately reflects the complexity of the industrial and economic system for which it serves as a linguistic expression.

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